

Sr. No	Prometabolite at different Time Interval	NIH3T3 Cells [IC ₅₀ (μg.mL ⁻¹)]
1	Blank - MRS	>50
2	24 th hour prometabolite (CFS)	>50
3	<3 Kda CFS fraction	>50
4	Pediocin (Sigma)	>50

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